

PETROLOGY OF LUNAR FELDSPATHIC BRECCIAS NORTHWEST AFRICA 11237, LARKMAN NUNATAK 06638, AND MILLER RANGE 07006. M. L. Meier¹, S. M. Elardo¹, C. G. Bunn¹, ¹Department of Geological Sciences, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611 (mckaylameier@ufl.edu)

Introduction: As we prepare for new lunar samples obtained through the Artemis missions, understanding the broader lunar crust through lithologies and clasts found in lunar meteorites remains an important avenue to accessing samples derived from outside the Procellarum KREEP Terrane (PKT). The Artemis exploration zone contains some of the oldest lunar compositions to be sampled [1-2], consisting of feldspathic highland terrain, composed of anorthositic, mafic, and ultramafic lithologies, in addition to impact and regolith compositions [1,3]. This study focuses on petrologic and geochemical analysis of clasts in a number of lunar meteorites with compositional characteristics (e.g., low Th and FeO) that make similar to lithologies expected at the south pole and in the farside highlands.

Northwest Africa 11237. Paired with the Northwest Africa 8222 clan, NWA 11237 represents a low shocked feldspathic fragmental breccia. Our sample reflects abundant small mineral and lithic clasts confined in a glassy groundmass with small vesicles.

Larkman Nunatak 06638. As an anorthositic regolith breccia, LAR 06638 uniquely reflects two lithologies [4]. Our sample is composed of dark and light groundmass areas, which divide the meteorite in a glassy region (dark) and a fragmental region (light).

Miller Range 07006. MIL 07006 is a basaltic-bearing regolith feldspathic breccia. Korotev et al. [5] hypothesizes that MIL 07006 is paired with Yamato 791197 regolith feldspathic breccia based on the whole rock geochemistry and petrologic texture. Similar to Joy et al. [6], our sample, MIL 07006,9, reflects a clast-dense breccia cemented together in a vesiculated, glassy groundmass with a partial fusion crust.

Methodology: This work examines the petrology and geochemistry of clasts within lunar regolith breccias, as a case study for potential sampling in the feldspathic highland terrane similar to that at the south pole. Lunar brecciated meteorites in this study exclude hypothesized PKT source components, focusing on materials that could be selected in south pole and/or farside missions.

Major and minor clast compositions were obtained using geochemical analyses of the Oxford Ultim Max 100 mm² silicon drift detector energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SDD-EDS) on Zeiss EVO MA10 scanning electron microscope (SEM) at the University of Florida (UF). High resolution grayscale backscatter electron imaging reveal clast and groundmass textures,

which are paired with elemental maps and quantitative phase analysis (Fig. 1).

Mineralogy: The lunar breccias in this study showcase a variety of textures and compositions. All breccias contain major mineral clasts of plagioclase, pyroxene, olivine, with accessory troilite, ilmenite, K-rich glass, and minor phosphates.

NWA 11237: NWA 11237 hosts primarily subhedral pyroxene clasts up to 600 μm diameters, with in compositions of $\text{Fs}_{19.1-61.3}\text{Wo}_{0.3-43.8}\text{En}_{16.4-68.0}$. Pyroxenes show chemical disequilibrium with variations in Fe and Ca contents, as well as exsolution textures. Highly fractured, anorthitic plagioclase ($\text{An}_{94.9-98.9}$) are prominent throughout NWA 11237, reflecting granulitic textures. Large pockets of impact melt are found throughout the sample, in which pyroxene, olivine ($\text{Fo}_{47.2-66.6}$), and plagioclase grains are encased in glass (heterogeneous). Minor phases of ulvöspinel (40 μm) were identified within larger plagioclase clasts.

LAR 06638: Anorthitic plagioclase (ranging from $\text{An}_{93.4}$ to An_{100}) is the dominant clast in LAR 06638, with smaller subhedral pyroxene ($\text{Fs}_{10.8-89.0}\text{Wo}_{2.2-53.2}\text{En}_{8.8-64.3}$) and olivine ($\text{Fo}_{34.9-65.0}$) clasts throughout. Accessory phases of ilmenite, spinel, troilite, and phosphates were also identified in the sample, as inclusions within larger fractured plagioclase grains. These minerals are found in both regions of the meteorite, in which the two lithologies share similar compositions but contrasting textures (glassy vs. fragmented). Anorthitic plagioclase granulitic clasts are prominent in the dark, glass matrix with lesser impact melts throughout the sample.

MIL 07006: Large mineral grains of anorthitic plagioclase ($\text{An}_{94.7-98.6}$) are found throughout the sample, which are highly fractured/granulitic and lack zoning. Smaller, euhedral pyroxene grains ($\text{Fs}_{18.3-84.9}\text{Wo}_{0.3-51.1}\text{En}_{2.0-65.8}$) were identified, in which they show exsolution textures. Subhedral, fractured olivine grains ($\text{Fo}_{27.5-80.2}$) and ilmenite grains are commonly associated with plagioclase clasts. Large, brecciated impact melt clasts were also identified, similar to such found in Joy et al. [6].

Future Work: Trace element clast analysis is being conducted through in situ laser ablation using the Element2 magnetic sector inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry facility at UF. Such work incorporates the procedures of Chen et al. [7], utilizing the low-resolution mode to observe the rare earth elements without major element oversaturation.

Additional constraints on accessory mineral geochemistry is planned to be conducted.

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References: [1] Patterson R. V. et al. (2024) *JGR Planets*, 129(6). [2] Hiesinger H. et al. (2012) *JGR Planets*, 117 (E12). [3] Lemelin M. et al. (2022) *PSJ*, 3, 63. [4] Zeigler R. A. and Korotev R. L. (2013) *LPS XLIV*, Abstract #1767. [5] Korotev R. L. et al. (2009) *LPS XL*, Abstract #1137. [6] Joy K. H. et al. (2010) *LPS XLI*, Abstract #1793. [7] Chen J. et al. (2026) *Geochemica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 415, 56-70.

Figure 1. Paired Backscatter electron (BSE) imagery and elemental maps (colored) for NWA 11237 (left), LAR 06638 (center), and MIL 07006 (right) meteorites. Grayscale BSE imagery reflects the elemental density of the sample, with brighter features reflecting the heaviest compositions. Elemental maps reflect the Mg, Fe, Ca, Na, Al, and Ti abundances for the correlating BSE images. Samples contain a variety of compositions and textures, including plagioclase (Pl), olivine (Ol), pyroxene (Pyx), ilmenite (Ilm), troilite (Troil), and impact melt (IM).